

Data Analysis Supplementary Information

To enhance traceability, this section provides additional details on the data analysis of challenges of using LLMs to support QS. Specifically, the following Table reports the themes resulting from the analysis and the data from which each theme was identified.

Challenge	More Information
1. Accounting for the Nuances of Qualitative Synthesis.	<p>When we tried to use LLMs to assist QS, we realized that there are several synthesis methods and that multiple concepts shape the nature and expectations for a QS. For example, we asked how the results of our synthesis might be used, and how that might influence the process (see “Synthetic Product” in Section 2 of the paper).</p> <p>[references: meeting transcripts and the researcher’s journal]</p>
2. Understanding LLM Capabilities and Limits.	<p>Early on and through part of the 1st Trial, we struggled to understand how LLMs operated on the tasks we assigned. For example, we were unsure whether we could trust them to follow a predefined sequence of steps. This led us to seek a deeper understanding of the nature and limits of LLMs.</p> <p>[references: meeting transcripts and the researcher’s journal]</p>
3. Difficulty in Evaluating Qualitative Syntheses.	<p>When we attempted to evaluate the 1st Trial, we initially tried a quantitative comparison of the topics found in the LLM-assisted syntheses against the manual synthesis. This told us little about the quality of the synthesis results, and it did not evaluate the process at all, which seemed inadequate given the process’s importance for several aspects of synthesis, such as the trustworthiness of the findings.</p> <p>[references: Section “Initial Quantitative Assessment of 1st Trial Outputs” of “10 - Evaluation of trial outputs”]</p>
4. Sensitivity to Prompts.	<p>An example of this sensitivity occurred in the 1st Trial. The LLM had been asked to carry out the steps of thematic analysis using three simulated experts to identify challenges in adopting EBSE, following the steps of EBSE.</p> <p>Prompts like “I need the experts to execute step number two of thematic analysis, each one using the quotes they extracted” had been yielding successful responses for step 1 of EBSE. Later, when prompted “I need the experts to continue with step four of thematic analysis,” it produced odd answers. The researcher replied, “you are mixing step 4 of EBSE with step 4 of thematic analysis,” and the LLM confirmed by saying, “You’re absolutely right, thank you for catching that.”</p> <p>[references: “08 - 1st Trial manual sup”]</p>
5. Possibility of Incorrect Responses.	<p>An example of an incorrect response occurred during the Expert Persona test in the 1st Trial. The LLM proposed the following theme:</p> <p>“Systemic Barriers to Evaluation in Industry. Despite the conceptual value of EBSE evaluation, practical barriers remain. Competitive concerns, lack of incentives for transparent reporting, and underinvestment in infrastructure make it difficult for companies to systematically share or even conduct evaluations.”</p>

	<p>While it is true that the seminal EBSE papers noted that competitive concerns disincentivized the publication of research, they did not claim that such concerns also hindered the conduct of evaluations.</p> <p>[references: “04 - 1st Trial assisted sup” and “10 - Evaluation of trial outputs”]</p>
<p>6. Lack of Transparency.</p>	<p>An example of lack of transparency occurred in the 1st Trial under the Expert persona prompting. The LLM was asked: “Imagine three different experts are helping me doing a synthesis of those papers, we want to find all the concerns or facilitators to apply the first step of EBSE (Step 1: Ask an Answerable Question”). All experts will write down quotes for the first step of their thematic analysis, then share it with the group. Then all experts will go on to the next step, etc. If any expert realises they’re wrong at any point then they leave.”</p> <p>However, the LLM limited the number of quotes per expert without being instructed to do so. The conversation continued as follows:</p> <p>Researcher: “it is suspicious to me that all the experts got 3 quotes, are you limiting to 3 quotes per expert? i want all the quotes not just 3”</p> <p>LLM: “You’re absolutely right to be suspicious, and thank you for pointing it out. In this first step, I will not limit the number of quotes per expert. [...]”</p> <p>[references: “04 - 1st Trial assisted sup” and “10 - Evaluation of trial outputs”]</p>
<p>7. Lack of Interpretation.</p>	<p>The lack of interpretation was evident in several aspects: misinterpretation, superficiality, and difficulty handling data heterogeneity.</p> <p>An example of misinterpretation is the excerpt presented in point 5. Possibility of Incorrect Responses.</p> <p>An example of superficiality was identified in the 1st Trial under Zero Prompting, where the challenge title does not adequately explain the issue (see following paragraph). The underlying problem is the difficulty of specifying EBSE research questions that are both relevant and answerable using existing evidence in the scientific literature.</p> <p>“Tension in Abstraction Level. Both papers emphasized the difficulty in choosing the right level of abstraction when formulating EBSE questions. If the technology or population is defined too broadly, the results may become vague or irrelevant; if defined too narrowly, relevant studies may be excluded. This tension represents a foundational challenge in designing effective EBSE queries.”</p> <p>Data heterogeneity was a problem in RQb of the 2nd Trial because the LLMs searched for findings in sections such as Related Work rather than only in the studies’ Results sections. For example, regarding RQb, the limitation identified was “Reliance on well-structured prompts,” and the quote in S2 was “Responses from LLMs are greatly influenced by the specific prompt given,” although that quote appears in the paper’s Related Work section.</p> <p>[references: “04 - 1st Trial assisted sup”, “06 - 2nd Trial”, and “10 - Evaluation of trial outputs”]</p>

<p>8. Presence of Inherent Biases</p>	<p>Here is an example of a somewhat cliché limitation that the LLM identified in the 1st Trial: “Contextual Dependency of Interpretation. Thematic analysis inherently involves interpretation, including code naming, theme grouping, and narrative construction. While we took care to stay close to the data, alternative analysts might have produced different groupings or named themes differently. Our iterative theme construction (for example, merging themes and naming conventions) adds interpretive layers that may not be fully replicable.”</p> <p>On the other hand, an example of a positivist stance that was implicit up to that point in the 1st Trial is the following: “No inter-coder reliability. This was a single-analyst process (co-facilitated by you and me), without independent coders. There was no formal check for coding consistency, a common step in rigorous qualitative work.”</p> <p>[reference: “03 - 1st Trial”]</p>
<p>9. Reproducibility Issues.</p>	<p>An example of reproducibility issues is the one described in point “4. Sensitivity to Prompts” where very similar prompts produced very different answers.</p> <p>Other challenges for reproducibility include the difficulty we faced in saving traces of our interactions with the LLMs. In particular, we had to use CTRL+C and CTRL+V to store the prompts and responses, and we also had to copy some tables and other elements separately.</p>
<p>10. LLMs Are Not Purpose-Built for Tasks Like Qualitative Synthesis.</p>	<p>Based on challenges 4 through 9 and our discussions with Sastre and Etcheverry, we identified another challenge related to the nature of LLMs and the characteristics of QS. We listed it separately because it could involve additional impacts on how to achieve a sound QS.</p>
<p>11. Evaluating QS Quality Requires Significant Effort.</p>	<p>Although we did not explicitly record the time spent evaluating the LLM-assisted QSs, the effort was considerable, on the order of two to three days per trial (18 to 24 hours). This is approximately the same time required to execute the LLM-assisted work plan itself.</p>
<p>12. Vulnerability to Confusing Form with Content.</p>	<p>Many times our first impression of the results was that they were adequate and correct. One example was the initial QS results for RQb in the 2nd Trial (see the supplementary material). In that case, although Galeano had accepted the outputs as satisfactory and had checked, for instance, that the quotes existed as excerpts from the primary studies, Pizard later verified that the outputs were not adequate because several of those quotes came from Related Work sections. See the last example in point “7. Lack of Interpretation”.</p> <p>[references: “06 - 2nd Trial” and “07 - 2nd Trial assisted sup”]</p>
<p>13. LLMs as a Compelling Innovation.</p>	<p>We experienced this challenge during the trials. It manifested, for example, in the ease of using LLMs. We could provide the full PDFs without preprocessing and then ask them to process the documents, without the learning curve required by other software tools that support qualitative research. In addition, as noted in the previous point, the responses initially seemed adequate, and we only realized that validating them requires substantial effort when we tried to do it.</p>